

Stabilizing Smiles: The Gunning Splint's Role in Mandibular Fracture Management

Received on : 18-07-2024 | Accepted on : 24-07-2024 | Published on : 04-09-2024

Dr. Praveen Kumar.P¹
Dr. Amit Kumar Sharma²
Dr. Vikram Sharma³
Dr. Sivaraman V⁴
Dr. Utham Chand B⁵
Dr. Kiran Yadav⁶

¹PG Student,
Department of Oral and
Maxillofacial Surgery,
NIMS Dental College and Hospital,
Jaipur, Rajasthan, India

²Professor and Head,
Department of Oral and
Maxillofacial Surgery,
NIMS Dental College and Hospital,
Jaipur, Rajasthan, India

³Professor,
Department of Oral and
Maxillofacial Surgery,
NIMS Dental College and Hospital,
Jaipur, Rajasthan, India

⁴Private Practitioner,
Prosthodontics and Oral Implantology,
Kumbakonam, Tamil Nadu, India

⁵PG Student,
Department of Oral and
Maxillofacial Surgery,
NIMS Dental College and Hospital,
Jaipur, Rajasthan, India

⁶PG Student,
Department of Oral and
Maxillofacial Surgery,
NIMS Dental College and Hospital,
Jaipur, Rajasthan, India

Corresponding Author
Dr. Praveen Kumar
PG Student,
Department of Oral and
Maxillofacial Surgery,
NIMS Dental College and Hospital,
Jaipur, Rajasthan, India

Abstract

Treating partially dentate or edentulous patients for fixation of fractured maxilla / mandible poses a challenge for the operator in case of elderly patients. The 'Gunning splint' initially was presented by Thomas Brain Gunning (1813–1889). Possibility of complications in elderly patients are more when compared to younger patients. Gunning splints provide closed reduction and better stabilization.

Keywords: Edentulous mandible, Gunning splint, Mandibular Fracture

Introduction

Road Traffic accidents are most common etiology for facial fracture. Treating partially dentate or edentulous patients for fixation of fractured maxilla/ mandible poses a challenge for the operator in case of elderly patients¹. For edentulous patients, treatment planning poses greater difficulties during reduction and fixation of fractured atrophic mandible. Due to edentulism, guidelines provided by occluding teeth for reduction and fixation of fracture, are absent. Open Reduction Internal Fixation is also not possible in case of immunocompromised elderly patients. The 'Gunning splint' initially was presented by Thomas Brain Gunning (1813–1889) for the immobilization of edentulous or partially edentulous jaw segments after reduction¹. A Gunning splint for the edentulous mandible consists of a type of mono block resembling two bite blocks joined together. These splints take form of modified dentures with bite block placed in posterior region and a space in incisal area to facilitate feeding. Intermaxillary splinting can be done by connecting two splints with wire loops or elastic bands².

Case Report

A 59 year old male patient reported to the NIMS Dental college with a complaint of swelling of the face resulting from a road traffic accident. The patient was examined by oral and maxillofacial surgery team in the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery. The examination revealed swelling

over the right and left side of the face extending from angle of mouth to angle of mandible bilaterally (fig 1). Laceration was present on the lingual surface of lower lip. There was no periorbital or sub-conjunctival ecchymosis. Intraoral examination revealed limited mouth opening. Hematoma was present on the floor of the mouth (Fig 2). Patient had been advised for NCCT Face which reveals right parasymphysis and left angle of mandible fracture. Fracture line was extending till the base of the mandible in vertically favourable manner. (Fig 3)

Then patient has been planned for closed reduction of the fractured mandible with Gunning splint instead of open reduction and internal fixation. The patient was moderately built and conscious. After initial first aid and cleaning of the wounds the patient was referred to the Department of Prosthodontics for the fabrication of gunning splint for the purpose of stabilizing the fractured segment. The initial impressions with alginate (irreversible hydrocolloid) impression material (Dentsply Zelgan Plus) was taken for both mandibular and maxillary arch (Fig 4). Impressions were immediately poured in dental stone to obtain casts and a heat cure splint was fabricated. (Fig 5).

Mandibular splint was designed with stoppers which would occlude with the maxillary splint and helps to keep that splint in

How to Cite This Article: Kumar P et al. : Stabilizing Smiles - The Gunning Splint's Role in Mandibular Fracture Management. AJOAD. 2024

Access this article online Website : www.updent.in	
DOI	Quick Response Code:

place. The splints were checked in patient's mouth for extension and frenum relief.

Then finishing and polishing of splints was carried out and they were disinfected in glutaraldehyde solution. First the maxillary splint was fixed with per-alveolar wiring. Close reduction of mandibular segments were carried out with hand manipulation of fracture segments to their approximate position. The tissue side of mandibular splint was relined with low fusing impression compound. This was done to compensate for any discrepancy between the splint and the mandible and also to provide firm immobilization of mandibular segments. Mandibular splint was fixed by circum-mandibular wiring (Fig 6). After securing the splints to the underlying bone, intermaxillary fixation was done with arch wires to provide firm immobilization. This was kept for 6 weeks after which it was replaced with elastics.

Discussion

As age progresses, significant changes occur in the functional vascular supply of mandible³. Healing will be delayed thus open reduction and internal fixation method is not preferred⁴. A careful history, oral and facial examination and complete radiographic survey are imperative whenever any fracture is suspected. The treatment options should be evaluated according to the patient's need and appropriate case selection with the dental team by careful treatment planning and interdisciplinary cooperation. Immobilization is carried out by attaching the upper splint to maxilla by para-alveolar wiring and lower splint to the mandibular body by circumferential wires. Intermaxillary splinting can be done by connecting two splints with wire loops or elastic bands. Close reduction with Gunning splint is advantageous because, not only it preserves the periosteal blood supply, but also provides firm mandibular fixation and immobilization.

Conclusion

In almost all the cases with edentulous mandibular fracture, a satisfactory union of fracture is obtained with Gunning splints than Open reduction internal fixation. Fabrication of Gunning splints is easy, Cost effective and comfort to the patients. Thus Gunning splints are preferred over open reduction internal fixation for edentulous mandible fracture.

References

1. Moodie F. Mr. Gunning and his splints. *Br J Oral Surg* 1969;7:112-5.
2. Zaki HS, Dantini DC, Aramany MA (1983) Compound splint for comminuted mandibular fracture. *J Prosthet Dent* 50:672-676.
3. Barber H, Woodbury S, Fonseca R (1997) *Oral and Maxillofacial trauma*. vol 3, WB Saunders, Philadelphia, pp. 473-526.
4. Siadat H, Arshad M, Shirani G, Alikhasi M (2012) New method for fabrication of Gunning splint in orthognathic surgery for edentulous patients. *J Dent Tehran* Summer 9(3):262-266.

Figure 1: Photograph showing extra oral swelling

Figure 2: Photograph showing intraorally

Figure 3: Photograph showing NCCT Face

Figure 4: Photograph showing Alginate impressions

Figure 5: Photograph showing fracture line marked on cast

Figure 6: Photograph showing Gunning Splint